

History of the Renovation of Abdulazizkhan Madrasah

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Abstract: This article covers the history of protection, repair and restoration of Abdulazizkhan madrasa during the 20-80s of the 20th century. Also, on the basis of the documents of the National Archives of Uzbekistan and the State Archives of Bukhara Region, the issues such as the scope of the renovation of the madrasa, the allocated funds, and the exploitation of the monument have been clarified.

Keywords: Bukhkomstaris, Sredazkomstaris, Bukhara Special Scientific and Restoration Production Enterprise, I.I. Umnyakov, V.A. Shishkin, Master ShirinMurodov, Ochil Bobomurodov, technical inspection.

Introduction

One of the magnificent monuments of Bukhara architecture is the 17th century Abdulazizkhan madrasah. Behind the four porches of the madrasah, there are semicircular doors leading to the side chambers. The chambers in the madrasah are two-storied, each consisting of a hall and a masonry oven. All types of architectural decorations known at the time, such as carved mosaics, colorful majolica with sculptural gorgon figures, patterns carved on gypsum, brick mosaic of facades and gold-plated patterns on a bright blue background, can be seen here.

Materials and Methods

The names of the masters who built the madrasah are skillfully carved among the tiles of the madrasah. These names belonged to the chief architect of the palace, Muhammad Salih, the calligrapher Muhammad Amin, and his son, leader Mimkhokans. However, where the craftsmen are from (genealogy) is not indicated here. From these names it can be assumed that the craftsmen were local masters. In Muhammad Yusuf Munshi's work "Tarihi Muqimkhani" the following is mentioned in the text of the inscription in this madrasah: "*..despite the weakness of his eyes, Maulana Muhammad Amin, who became a master of calligraphs, writes in suls calligraph...*" [1].

However, with the passage of time, under the influence of various natural and artificial factors, the madrasah was damaged and decayed. In order to prevent this, it was repaired in different ways in different stages of history.

Results

Bukhara Committee for Museum Works, Ancient Monuments and Art and Nature Protection (Bukhkomstaris), which was established in the early 20s of the 20th century, is one of the institutions that gained significant importance in the protection of Bukhara's architectural monuments, their repair and restoration.

Since this period, the work of studying monuments on a planned basis began. In particular, on October 7, 1924, an initial technical inspection was carried out to determine the condition of the Abdulazizkhan madrasah under the leadership of Musa Saidjonov, the Minister of Education of the BSSR, with the participation of architects M. Ya. Ginsburg and V. A. Krasilnikov. During the

inspection, 40-50% of the mosaic and majolica decorations were preserved in the front part (facade) of Abdulazizkhan madrasa, and 20% in the inner courtyard. It is also observed that the entrance gate of the madrasa is damaged (2 sq m) and there is a crack in the gate on the left side of the front. It was determined that 15% of the roof needed plastering.

On October 23, 1924, based on the conclusions of the technical inspection, works such as plastering the inner and outer walls of the monument, cleaning the roof, picking bricks (10 cubic meters), restoring brick mosaics and strengthening the existing ones were determined [2].

Discussion

During the study of archival documents, it became clear that the registration of historical monuments considered significant in the republic was carried out. Abdulazizkhan madrasah was included in this list, which was formed on May 4, 1925, among the 18 architectural monuments in Bukhara [3].

In the 20-80s of the 20th century, a system of renting out monuments was created in order to create a special budget for the repair of monuments.

On October 15, 1927, the Central Asian Committee on Museum Works, Ancient Monuments and Art and Nature Protection (Sredazkomstaris) discussed the issue of renting the Abdulazizkhan madrasah as a prison. In the decision part of the meeting it is said: *"..In this case, we express our principled opposition to renting out the historical monument for civic purposes. However, the committee (Sredazkomstaris–D.A.) prefers to grant permission under certain conditions based on the situation in Bukhara"* [4]. These requirements included the obligation of the Executive Committee to repair the monument in agreement with the Bukhkomstaris and Sredazkomstaris, to maintain the original condition of the building, and to pay the rent.

The trend of abandoning monuments, which grew during the years of Soviet rule, had a negative impact on Abdulazizkhan madrasah. In particular, for this purpose, on March 22-31, 1927, I.I. Umnyakov, who worked as the head of the Art and Ancient Monuments Protection Department of (Sredazkomstaris), made a business trip to Bukhara, is a clear proof of this. In Bukhara, on February 20, 1927, the workers of the Oblgormestkhoz began to demolish two architectural monuments of the 17th century, Poyanda-biy and Abdulaziz Khan madrasahs. The appeals of Bukhkomstaris to the Bukhara City Executive Committee to stop these cases were not resolved positively.

The analysis of documents shows that the deputy chairman of the city's executive committee, Mukamilov, in his reply letter addressed to Bukhkomstaris stated that the Poyanda-bi mosque in Registan square is of no historical importance, and stated that the demolition work will continue, and the work on Abdulaziz Khan madrasa will be stopped. In particular, when I.I. Umnyakov visited, 9 arches on the west side of the madrasah were completely demolished. As a result of the scientist's visit to Bukhara, a report on the attitude of the city's executive committee to the monuments was drawn up and sent to the Public Education Committee. These events are described in the following report: *"...As a result of my visit to Bukhara, I witnessed a monument that could not be restored, and I asked Mr. Butkevich to take a picture of it. As for the Madrasah of Abdulazizkhan, it needs to be restored.."* [5]¹.

As a result of these efforts, the most important thing was to prevent the complete destruction of Abdulazizkhan madrasah. After that, special importance was also given to the supply of monuments.

In 1930-1931, the crumbling stalactites (muqarnas) and sharafas on the main portal of Abdulazizkhan madrasah were restored by Usta Abdusalam and Aminjon Salomov under the leadership of Usta Shirin Muradov. In 1934, 70 types of repair works were determined in the

¹ National archive of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Fund-P-394, Registry 1, Folio 266, Page 42.

madrasa, and funds in the amount of 153,069 rubles 08 pennies were allocated based on the estimate documents[6].

From the report documents of Bukhkomstaris organization in 1936, it was known that the outer side of the wall of the second floor of the Abdulazizkhan madrasah, the porch of the inner courtyard and the part of the porch were repaired, and the dome and the roof of the madrasah were covered with square-shaped baked bricks.6,230 rubles were spent on the completed works[7].

Abdulaziz Khan madrasa was used not only for renting, but also for the purpose of organizing exhibitions and fairs. Also, in 1937, under the leadership of V. A. Shishkin, the exhibition on the theme “Architectural ceramic ornaments, patterns and examples of engraving”, where wall decorations of Magoki attar and ancient courtyards were displayed, is a clear proof of this.

Analysis and results

As a result of scientific research carried out by the Department of Architectural Works in 1949, Abdulazizkhan and Mirzo Ulugbek madrasas were scientifically described as a Kosh madrasah complex, and the drawings were included in the city’s general plan. This year, 22,148 rubles were allocated for the repair of the monument, cleaning of the damaged areas of the roof, restoration of the southwest corner of the dome and bouquet of the building, covering the stairs, roof and dome with bricks [8].

However, on August 4, 1949, based on the order of the Council of Ministers of the UZSSR, the head of the Department of Architectural Works V.A. Jahongirov sent an appeal to Yusupov, the regional representative in Bukhara. In this appeal, it is noted that ten of the architectural monuments of Bukhara will be allocated for a period of 6 months as warehouses of the enterprise “Zagotzerno” (for the purpose of wheat storage - D.A.), the rent amount will be calculated in the amount of 12 pennies per 1 sqm[9]. Among these architectural monuments there was Abdulazizkhan madrasah.

Scientific documents show that until September 1951, Abdulazizkhan madrasah served as the military commissariat (voenkomat) of the city[10].

From May 6, 1953, according to the conclusion of the executive committee of the city of Bukhara, the madrasah was rented for 3 months for patients suffering from infectious disease-dysentery[11]. And the sick were accommodated in madrasah cells.

When the report documents of 1954 were studied, it was revealed that the repair works in the amount of 38,026 rubles were carried out in Abdulazizkhan Madrasah.

In 1957, based on the conclusions of the scientific research sector of the Bukhara Special Scientific and Restoration Production Enterprise, an extended report on the technical condition of the madrasah was drawn up and the scope of repair work was determined. According to him, the covering part of the walls of the madrasah yard was repaired and work was carried out to strengthen the decoration of the porch. Also, stalactites (muqarnas) on the portal of the courtyard was restored to its original state by the master-architect from Bukhara, Ochil Bobomurodov, and his disciples[12].

By 1968, as a result of the introduction of the Abdulazizkhan madrasah into the tourist route, the madrasah underwent large-scale renovations. In particular, repair work was carried out on the facade of the monument, on the wall of the cells in the southern part of the inner courtyard[13].

In 1973, the reconstruction of the cell arches and the beautification of the protected area of the madrasah were carried out. The analysis of data on the renovation of the Abdulazizkhan madrasa shows that it was used as the building of the Monuments Protection Inspectorate since 1979[14].

Conclusions

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of the erosion of monuments under the influence of various factors, the way of learning and passing on the development of culture to the next

generation may be closed. Based on these characteristics, today the history of the restoration of historical monuments and the processes related to them is important.

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